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Variation in breast milk macronutrient contents by maternal anemia and hemoglobin concentration in northern Kenya

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Abstract

Objectives: This study explored differing levels of macronutrients in breast milk in relation to maternal anemia and hemoglobin.

Methods: Archived milk specimens and data from a cross-sectional sample of 208 breastfeeding mothers in northern Kenya, originally collected in 2006, were analyzed; data included milk fat, maternal hemoglobin concentration, and anemia status (anemia defined as hemoglobin <12 g/dl). Total protein and lactose were measured and energy was calculated. To explore the association between milk outcomes (fat, protein, lactose, and energy) and anemia, regression models were constructed with and without adjustment for maternal age, parity, and time (days) postpartum. The same models were constructed using hemoglobin as a continuous predictor in lieu of dichotomous anemia to explore the role of hemoglobin levels and anemia severity in predicting milk outcomes.

Results: The group comparison indicated significantly higher milk protein and lower milk fat for anemic mothers relative to non-anemic counterparts. After adjustment for maternal age, parity, and time postpartum, maternal anemia was associated with significantly higher milk protein ($p=0.001$) and significantly lower milk fat ($p=0.025$). Hemoglobin had a significant inverse relationship with milk protein ($p=0.017$) and a marginally significant positive relationship with milk fat ($p=0.060$) after adjusting for the maternal variables. Neither anemia nor hemoglobin was significant in predicting lactose or milk energy.

Conclusions: Maternal anemia and hemoglobin concentration may be associated with complex changes in milk macronutrients. Future research should clarify the impact of maternal anemia on a range of breast milk components while accounting for other maternal characteristics.

Keywords: anemia, hemoglobin, protein, milk fat, lactose, breast milk

Introduction

Anemia is a blood disorder that affects millions of people with functional impairments worldwide (Benoist, Mclean, Egll, & Cogswell, 2008). This disorder is defined as a subnormal level of hemoglobin, an oxygen transporter protein in the red blood cell. Iron deficiency is the most common cause of anemia; however, deficiencies in other micronutrients (e.g. folate), elevated inflammation, and infectious disease processes can all cause anemia. This is also true for individuals who are seemingly healthy with normal BMI.

Maternal anemia is particularly important to study since it can have adverse consequences not only for the mother, but also for her offspring. Previous studies have found that maternal anemia is associated with low birth weight or preterm birth (Picciano, 2003), elevated risks for infantile/childhood anemia (Meinzen-Derr et al., 2006; Pee et al., 2002), and, in severe cases of maternal anemia, an elevated risk for child mortality (Murray-Kolb & Beard, 2007; Picciano, 2003). The biological reasoning for these associations is unclear. It is plausible that alterations in breast milk may be a pathway through which maternal anemia impacts infant health.

Existing literature indicates that maternal anemia is associated with altered concentrations of milk components. Since breast milk may be the sole source of nutrients for infants during the first months of life, these alterations in breast milk may put infants of anemic mothers at higher health risks in some environments. El-Farrash, Ismail, & Nada (2012) assessed the effect of maternal iron deficiency anemia on milk micronutrients among mothers in Egypt. They found that maternal anemia was associated with decreased milk micronutrients (iron, copper, zinc, calcium, and magnesium); this decrease was further amplified among mothers with moderate to severe anemia. In the same study, infants born to mothers with anemia were also more likely to have lower hemoglobin levels, serum iron, and transferrin saturation percentage. Another study among Indian women similarly found that milk iron content was significantly lower in severely anemic mothers; however, this was not significant with mild-to-moderate anemia (Kumar, Kumar Rai, Basu, Dash, & Singh, 2008). The same study also found that maternal hemoglobin and blood iron levels were correlated with breast milk iron levels (Kumar et al., 2008). Working with mothers in Brazil, França et al., (2013) further found that maternal anemia may alter immunological and nutritional milk components differently depending on the lactational stage (colostrum, transitional, or mature milk).

The literature, however, remains limited on how maternal anemia may impact milk macronutrients. Macronutrients are important to examine because they form the building blocks for human development in terms of

structure and function. Previous studies on the associations between milk macronutrients and maternal characteristics tended to focus on maternal dietary intake, maternal BMI (as a general nutritional status indicator), and lactation stage (e.g. Chang et al., 2015; Dewey, Finley, & Lönnerdal, 1984; Quinn, Largado, Power, & Kuzawa, 2012), but have rarely investigated maternal anemia. Anemia can be prevalent among women with normal BMI depending on their micronutrient nutrition, infectious disease history or status, or recent blood loss, each of which can cause anemia. It may be reasonable to expect that the effect of maternal anemia on milk macronutrients will be different from that of maternal BMI or general nutrition.

This study aimed to examine the association of maternal anemia and milk macronutrients (fat, lactose, and total protein) and energy (kcal), while adjusting for other maternal characteristics. In line with a previous study on milk micronutrients by El-Farrash et al. (2012), and in light of the reported association of maternal anemia with adverse offspring health parameters, it was hypothesized that maternal anemia would be associated with a decrease in milk macronutrient concentration.

Methods

Archived milk specimens from a cross-sectional sample of 208 breastfeeding Ariaal mothers in northern Kenya, originally collected in 2006 for research on micronutrient health of seemingly healthy mothers (Fujita, 2008), were analyzed. The mothers were residents of sedentary agro-pastoral Ariaal communities; their transition from nomadic pastoral subsistence mode, and the ecological, sociocultural, and nutritional contexts of their sedentarization have been described in depth elsewhere (Fratkin, 2004; Fratkin & Roth, 1990, 2005; Fratkin & Smith, 1995; Fujita, 2003; Fujita, Roth, Nathan, & Fratkin, 2004, 2005; Miller, 2010; Roth & Fratkin, 2005; Roth & Ngugi, 2005; Shell-Duncan & Yung, 2004). Mothers in these communities are ideal for this study given that they tended to exclusively breastfeed long-term.

In the original study, data were collected from consenting mothers under an approval of the community chiefs and the internal review boards of the University of Washington and Kenya Medical Research Institute. Data collection took place during a prolonged drought and food shortage; many mothers were coping with the food shortage by reducing food variety, meal size or the number of meals for their consumption (Apland & Fujita, 2013, 2014, 2015; Apland, Fujita, & Chang, 2016; Fujita, 2008; Fujita, Apland, & Chang, 2016), and prioritizing their children in allocating limited amount of foods within households (Fujita, 2008). Our subsequent research found that low BMI (Fujita, 2008; Fujita, Brindle, Lo,

Castro, & Cameroamortegui, 2014), vitamin A deficiency (Fujita, 2008; Fujita et al., 2011, 2017a), and iron deficiency (Fujita et al., 2018ab; Fujita & Wander, 2017) were prevalent among these mothers.

Milk and blood sample collection methods have been described in depth elsewhere (Fujita, 2008; Fujita et al., 2011, 2017a; Fujita & Wander, 2017). In brief, breast milk collection took place following an overnight fast. Assisted by research staff, each mother manually expressed a small amount of foremilk into a paper cup from whichever breast that was refrained from nursing overnight. Milk samples were immediately transferred to polypropylene tubes and frozen. Mothers were free to breastfeed their infants upon milk sample collection. Venous blood was drawn immediately after milk collection, and hemoglobin concentration was assessed using a drop of fasting venous blood sample and a portable hemoglobinometer (Hemocue Hb201+). Maternal anemia status was determined using hemoglobin level of <12 g/dL as the cut-off, and anemic mothers were referred to a clinic. Other maternal characteristics (age, parity, time postpartum) and fat concentration determined via creatocrit were also available from the original study (Fujita, 2008; Fujita et al., 2011).

Between 2017 and 2018, the concentrations of lactose and milk protein were determined using cryogenically archived milk in the Biomarker Laboratory for Anthropological Research of Michigan State University. Thawed milk specimens were triple-centrifuged at 4°C to obtain clear sera. Lactose was determined through an enzyme-based assay (BioAssay Systems, Hayward, CA, Cat. No. ELAC-100). The within-assay CVs were 6.6% and 2.8% for in-house and external controls, respectively, and the between-assay CVs were 8.6% and 14.9% for 15 plates. Milk total protein was determined using a microBCA assay (Thermo Scientific, Cat. No. 23235). The within-assay CVs were 7.3% and 1.5%, and between-assay CVs were 2.5% and 12.6% across 7 plates. For both assays, the certified standard reference material of the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST1549a) was used as the external controls. Milk energy was calculated by use of the following equation from Miller et al. (2013): $9.25(\text{fat}) + 5.65(\text{protein}) + 3.95(\text{lactose})$.

Data were analyzed in Stata version 13. The data for fat and total protein were transformed using natural log to correct for skewed distribution. Descriptive statistics were assessed to summarize the characteristics of the sample overall and by anemia group. Scatter plots were constructed and pairwise correlations were tested to assess bivariate relationships between milk variables, hemoglobin, and other maternal variables. To evaluate the relationship between each of the breast milk macronutrients/energy outcomes and maternal anemia or continuous hemoglobin, regression models were constructed without any adjustment (crude) and with adjustment for maternal age, parity, and time postpartum (adjusted).

In these models, standardized values of hemoglobin, maternal age, and time postpartum, and the observed value minus one for parity (so that parity of zero represents primiparous mothers) were utilized. Residuals plots and variance inflation factors were utilized to diagnose possible violation of regression assumptions. Predicted values from adjusted models were utilized to produce a graphical summary of the relationship between each of the milk outcomes and hemoglobin.

Results

The characteristics of the sample are summarized in **Table 1**. The mean maternal age was 27.9 years (range of 18-46 years), mean parity was 3.6 (range of 1-12), and mean time postpartum was 244 days (range of 24-585 days). Fifty one mothers (25%) were anemic, and the remaining 157 mothers were non-anemic. Compared to non-anemic mothers, anemic mothers were significantly younger (25.6 ± 6.1 years vs. 28.7 ± 6.7 , $p=0.005$), had significantly lower parity (2.8 ± 1.8 vs. 3.9 ± 2.3 , $p = 0.002$), and shorter time postpartum (208 ± 134 vs. 256 ± 134 , $p = 0.029$). Milk total protein was significantly higher (1.08 ± 0.19 g/dl vs. 0.96 ± 0.16 , $p < 0.001$) while milk fat was significantly lower for anemic mothers (Mean \pm SD 2.24 ± 1.24 g/dl vs. 2.68 ± 1.27 , $p=0.035$) when compared to non-anemic mothers. Lactose concentration showed no significant difference between the two groups (7.95 ± 1.2 g/dl vs. 7.74 ± 1.2 , $p = 0.276$). Despite the differences in fat and protein, milk energy was not significantly different between anemic and non-anemic mothers (58.22 ± 12.34 Kcal/dl vs. 60.74 ± 12.73 , $p = 0.218$). **Figure 1** graphically summarizes the distribution of each milk outcome in relation to maternal variables.

Anemia

Table 2 summarizes regression models. In the crude model, anemia had a significant positive association with milk protein ($\beta = 0.11$, $p < 0.001$), a significant inverse association with milk fat ($\beta = -0.18$, $p = 0.02$), a non-significant positive association with lactose ($\beta = 0.21$, $p = 0.276$), and a non-significant inverse association with milk energy ($\beta = -0.04$, $p = 0.226$). After adjustment for age, parity, and time postpartum, anemia's associations with milk outcomes essentially remained unchanged; it had a significant positive association with milk protein ($\beta = 0.09$, $p = 0.001$), a significant inverse association with milk fat ($\beta = -0.17$, $p = 0.025$), a non-significant positive association with lactose ($\beta = 0.20$, $p = 0.303$) and a non-significant inverse association with energy ($\beta = -0.04$, $p = 0.242$). Of the adjustment variables, maternal parity was a marginal predictor of milk fat ($p=0.1$). Time postpartum was a significant inverse predictor of milk

protein ($p < 0.001$), significant positive predictor of milk fat ($p = 0.028$), significant inverse predictor of lactose ($p = 0.003$), and non-significant positive predictor of milk energy ($p = 0.550$).

Hemoglobin

In the crude model, hemoglobin had a significant inverse relationship with milk protein ($\beta = -0.04$, $p = 0.001$; Table 2), a significant positive relationship with milk fat ($\beta = 0.07$, $p = 0.027$), a non-significant inverse relationship with lactose ($\beta = -0.01$, $p = 0.901$), and a non-significant positive relationship with milk energy ($\beta = 0.02$, $p = 0.117$). After adjustment for age, parity, and time postpartum, hemoglobin had a significant inverse relationship with milk protein ($\beta = 0.03$, $p = 0.017$), a marginally significant positive relationship with milk fat ($\beta = 0.06$, $p = 0.060$), a non-significant inverse relationship with lactose ($\beta = 0.02$, $p = 0.774$), and a non-significant positive relationship with milk energy ($\beta = 0.02$, $p = 0.141$).

Of the adjustment variables, time postpartum was a significant inverse predictor of milk protein ($p < 0.001$), significant positive predictor of milk fat ($p = 0.036$), significant inverse predictor of lactose ($p = 0.002$), and non-significant positive predictor of milk energy ($p = 0.659$). Neither maternal age nor parity had a significant relationship with any of the milk outcomes. **Figure 2** provides a visual summary of the relationships between milk outcomes and hemoglobin after adjusting for other maternal variables. The graph for milk protein displays a relatively steep downward slope in milk protein concentration along the hemoglobin spectrum, with the highest quartile of the predicted protein concentrations all falling within the anemic region (<12 g/dl). Contrastingly, the graph for milk fat displays a relatively steep positive slope, with the majority of lowest predicted fat concentrations occupying the anemic region. These unidirectional slopes indicate that the degree of severity of maternal anemia had a systematic quantitative relationship with the variation in milk protein and fat content – i.e. the lower the hemoglobin level (i.e. the more severe the anemia), the greater the difference from non-anemic mothers.

Discussion

This study explored macronutrient concentrations and energy value of breast milk by maternal anemia status and hemoglobin concentration. It was hypothesized that milk nutrients would be lower among anemic mothers when compared to non-anemic mothers. Our regression model results suggest, instead, that maternal anemia might have suppressive, enhancing, or no effects on milk macronutrient contents, and the direction of effects may depend on the

nutrient. With or without adjustments for possible influences from age, parity, and time postpartum, mothers with anemia had lower milk fat, higher protein, but no difference in lactose or energy in comparison to non-anemic mothers. Furthermore, maternal hemoglobin had a significant inverse relationship with milk protein and a significant (marginal with adjustments) positive relationship with milk fat, yet no relationship with lactose or energy.

In this harsh environment, anemic mothers may produce milk with lower fat and higher protein than mothers without anemia. It is possible that decreased fat and increased protein in milk may be a consequence of maternal physiological adjustments to better maintain her somatic condition under nutritional stress while still promoting her child's health. Protein may be more valuable to the growing child for tissue accretion while fat may be crucial for mothers facing high levels of nutritional stress. This shift in milk nutrient concentrations may also function as a way for mothers to maintain relatively stable milk energy, facilitating the buffering of infants from the impact of nutritional stress underlying maternal anemia (Pond, 1977; Quinn et al., 2012; Quinn, Diki Bista, & Childs, 2016; Fujita, Paredes Ruvalcaba, Wander, Corbitt, & Brindle., 2018ab) as part of evolved maternal strategy (Power & Schulkin, 2016). This interpretation is consistent with our observation of a non-significant association between maternal anemia and milk energy.

Anemia may represent undernourishment, which may coincide with low BMI. A number of studies have previously associated maternal undernutrition (e.g., low BMI) with reduced milk fat (e.g., Butte, Garza, Stuff, Smith, & Nichols, 1984; Chang et al., 2015; Grote et al., 2015; Michaelsen, Skafte, Badsberg, & Jorgensen, 1990; Nommsen, Lovelady, Heinig, Lonnerdal, & Dewey, 1991). Other studies (e.g., Butte & Calloway, 1981) have found that undernourished mothers may still produce milk fat within the normal range. Our results side with the literature reporting that maternal undernutrition may be associated with reduced milk fat. The literature on milk protein and maternal BMI is more variable; studies report a positive association (Grote et al., 2015; Chang et al., 2015; Michaelsen et al., 1990), an inverse association (Bachour, Yafawi, Jaber, & Choueiri, 2012), and no association (Butte & Calloway, 1981; Jelliffe, 1952; Quinn et al., 2012). Our study is more consistent with studies reporting an inverse relationship between milk protein and maternal nutrition.

With respect to other maternal characteristics, time postpartum was a significant positive predictor for milk fat, confirming multiple previous studies (Mandel, Lubetzky, Dollberg, Barak, & Mimouni, 2005; Quinn et al., 2012), but contradicting Dewey et al. (1984) which found no association between milk fat and time postpartum. Time postpartum was an inverse predictor of milk protein, confirming a previous study (Dewey et al., 1984).

The studies of milk macronutrients and maternal nutrition cited above looked at certain maternal characteristics, but rarely focused on maternal anemia or hemoglobin. Miller (2010) investigated associations between maternal characteristics and maternal hemoglobin and found that parity and time since birth are predictors of maternal hemoglobin. In the present study, after adjusting for the effects of parity and time postpartum, anemia remained significant in predicting milk protein and fat. Future research should replicate this study and further examine the impacts of other maternal characteristics on breast milk as another avenue of how maternal health may impact milk, and ultimately, infant well-being. Our team is currently investigating the effects of maternal micronutrient deficiencies, inflammation/infection, and anemia on milk in a separate study (Fujita et al., 2018ab).

A limitation of this study was that the milk specimens had been subjected to prolonged cryogenic storage at -80°C and underwent freeze/thaw cycles prior to being assayed. Lactose is sensitive to these processes (Lev et al., 2014), and thus, the data for this macronutrient may have been influenced. This influence is unlikely to pose a major bias to the study, for milk of anemic and non-anemic mothers have gone through the same freeze-thaw cycles. The lactose concentrations were comparable to those from other populations (Miller et al., 2013). Furthermore, the original study excluded mothers with clinical signs of infection such as fever or vomiting, and therefore the data may not be representative of the entire population.

Conclusion

Maternal anemia is a major public health concern worldwide that may affect breast milk components. Previous research has suggested that mothers with moderate to severe anemia may produce milk with decreased macronutrients; however, the research on this topic has remained limited. The results from our study suggest that decreases in milk macronutrients are likely the result of a complex interplay of several factors, of which maternal anemia is just one, and that some milk macronutrients may be unaffected, or even increase, in the presence of maternal anemia. Further research is necessary to understand these complexities as they may have potential impacts for maternal and infant health.

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Author Contributions

MF conceived the study. MC, NPR, and MF implemented the study. MC drafted the original manuscript as a short report. MC, NPR, and MF edited the manuscript for intellectual content. NPR and MF revised the manuscript for resubmission as a regular length original research article.

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Table 1 Characteristics of study participants overall and by anemia status ^a

Characteristic	Overall (n=208)	Anemia (n=51)	Non-Anemia (n=157)	<i>P</i> -value ^b
Maternal age (years)	27.9 (6.8) 18–46	25.6 (6.1) 18–42	28.7 (6.9) 18–46	.005
Parity	3.6 (2.2) 1–12	2.8 (1.8) 1–9	3.9 (2.3) 1–12	.002
Time postpartum (days)	244 (135) 24–585	208 (134) 32–520	256 (134) 24–585	.029
Hemoglobin (g/dl)	12.9 (1.8) 7.3–16.8	10.3 (1.2) 7.3–11.9	13.8 (1.0) 12–16.8	<.001
Milk total protein (g/dl)	0.99 (0.18) 0.7–1.6	1.08 (0.19) 0.7–1.6	0.96 (0.16) 0.7–1.5	<.001
Milk fat (g/dl)	2.57 (1.27) 0.9–7.8	2.24 (1.24) 0.9–7.8	2.68 (1.27) 0.9–6.9	.035
Lactose (g/dl)	7.79 (1.2) 4.7–11.2	7.95 (1.2) 5.6–11.0	7.74 (1.2) 4.7–11.2	.276
Milk energy (Kcal/dl)	60.1 (12.7) 35–112	58.2 (12.3) 43–112	60.7 (12.7) 35–96	.218

^a mean (SD) range^b t-test

Table 2 Regression models for breast milk macronutrients and energy (n=208)

Predictor	Breast milk outcome			
	ln(Milk protein) β (95% CI)	ln(Milk fat) β (95% CI)	Lactose conc. β (95% CI)	Milk energy β (95% CI)
<i>Anemia (Hemoglobin<12g/dl)</i>				
<i>Crude</i>				
Anemia	0.11** (0.06, 0.16)	-0.18* (-0.32, -0.03)	0.21 (-0.17, 0.59)	-0.04 (-0.10, 0.02)
<i>Adjusted^a</i>				
Anemia	0.09** (0.04, 0.14)	-0.17* (-0.32, -0.02)	0.20 (-0.19, 0.59)	-0.04 (-0.11, 0.03)
Maternal age, 1 SD	-0.01 (-0.04, 0.03)	0.04 (-0.06, 0.14)	0.09 (-0.16, 0.35)	0.03 (-0.02, 0.07)
Parity, 1 birth	-0.00 (-0.02, 0.01)	-0.04 [†] (-0.08, 0.01)	0.03 (-0.08, 0.15)	-0.01 (-0.03, 0.01)
Time postpartum, 1 SD	-0.04** (-0.07, -0.02)	0.07* (0.01, 0.13)	-0.24** (-0.41, -0.08)	0.01 (-0.02, 0.04)
<i>Hemoglobin (continuous, g/dl)</i>				
<i>Crude</i>				
Hemoglobin, 1 SD	-0.04** (-0.07, -0.02)	0.07* (0.01, 0.14)	-0.01 (-0.18, 0.16)	0.02 (-0.01, 0.05)
<i>Adjusted^a</i>				
Hemoglobin, 1 SD	-0.03* (-0.05, -0.01)	0.06 [†] (-0.00, 0.13)	0.02 (-0.15, 0.19)	0.02 (-0.01, 0.05)
Maternal age, 1 SD	-0.01 (-0.04, 0.03)	0.04 (-0.06, 0.14)	0.09 (-0.17, 0.34)	0.03 (-0.02, 0.07)
Parity, 1 birth	-0.00 (-0.02, 0.01)	-0.04 (-0.08, 0.01)	0.02 (-0.09, 0.14)	-0.01 (-0.03, 0.01)
Time postpartum, 1 SD	-0.04** (-0.07, -0.02)	0.07* (0.00, 0.13)	-0.26** (-0.43, -0.10)	0.01 (-0.02, 0.03)

^a Predictors in adjusted models = standardized hemoglobin, standardized maternal age, parity minus one, and standardized time (days) postpartum

** p<0.01; * p<0.05; † p<0.1

Figure 1 Distribution of milk variables in relation to maternal variables

Figure 2 Relationship of maternal hemoglobin with predicted milk outcomes (adjusted for maternal variables)